

The Influence of Work Environment and Organizational Culture on Organization Performance Through Motivation as a Mediation Variables on Pt. Semen Baturaja (PERSERO)

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Abstract: *This study aims to examine the influence of the work environment and organizational culture on organizational performance through motivation. The research was conducted at PT Semen Baturaja with a total sample of 114 employees who work at the company office. This sampling uses the saturated sample method because it uses all employees at the company office. The research instrument uses a questionnaire which will be arranged based on predetermined dimensions. The data analysis technique used path analysis.*

The results showed that work environment variables partially influence organizational performance. Work organizational culture variables partially influence organizational performance. Motivation variables partially influence organizational performance. Work environment variables partially influence motivation. Organizational culture variables affect motivation partially. The influence of the work environment on organizational performance is 0.532. The influence of the work environment on performance through motivation is $0.669 \times 0.861 = 0.576$. In this case, the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect, so it can be said that the work motivation variable is intervening. The direct effect of work organizational culture on organizational performance is 0.654. While the influence of work organizational culture on organizational performance through motivation is $0.780 \times 0.861 = 0.672$. In this case, the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect, so it can be said that the work motivation variable is intervening.

Keywords: *work environment, organizational culture, motivation, organizational performance*

I. Introduction

Organizational performance is what is produced by the organization which includes outcomes, namely financial performance such as profit as measured by return on assets, return on investment, and so on, market performance such as an expansion of market share, and sales. Also, the return from the shareowner is the return of the shareowner and the economic increase of the shareowner. In some areas of organizational performance can also be measured from other things such as strategic planning, operations, finance, legal and organizational development. Developing an institution or organization is a must to survive in the competitive climate of the world.

Organizational performance at PT. Semen Baturaja (Persero) is a company that produces cement and is owned by the state, so the status is the company. The organization's performance shows improvement. This is indicated by an increased level of productivity, an increase in the number of customers, an increase in financial performance, and customer satisfaction in receiving company services.

The definition of organizational performance refers to the ability of employees to carry out all the tasks that are their responsibility. These tasks are usually based on indicators of success that have been implemented.

As a result, it will be known that an employee enters a certain level of work. The level can be various terms. Performance can be categorized as over target, on target, or under target. Departing from the things referred to as a whole for the work of an employee. The definition of organizational performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity program or policy in realizing the goals, objectives, vision, and mission of the organization as outlined in the strategic planning of an organization (Moeheriono, 2010: 60). Mangkuprawira (2011: 218-219) says that performance is a matter, or the overall success rate of a person during a certain period in carrying out a task compared to various possibilities, such as work standards, targets, or targets or criteria that have been determined in advance and have been agreed together.

According to Wibowo (2016: 19), performance is a management style in managing performance-oriented resources that carries out an open and sustainable communication process by creating a common vision and strategic and integrated approach as a driving force to achieve organizational goals. According to Rivai and Sagala (2009: 548) suggest that: "Performance is a function of motivation and ability to complete a task or a person's work should have a certain degree of willingness and level of ability. According to Richard et al (2010), organizational performance is what is produced by the organization which includes results, namely financial performance such as profit as measured by return on assets, return on investment and so on, market performance such as market share expansion, and sales. Also, the return from the shareowner is the return of the shareowner and the economic increase of the shareowner.

Organizational performance is influenced by various factors, namely work environment, organizational culture, and motivation. According to Nitisemito (2000: 159), the work environment is an internal and external condition that can affect morale so that work can be expected to be completed faster and better. According to Sedarmayanti (2010: 12), the conditions of the work environment are said to be good or appropriate if humans can carry out activities in an optimal, healthy, safe, and comfortable manner. The impact of the suitability of the work environment can be seen in the long term. Furthermore, a less good work environment can demand more labor and time and does not support the obtaining of an efficient work system design.

The type of work environment is divided into two, namely: (a) The physical work environment is a physical condition that is around the workplace which can affect the person directly or indirectly (b) Non-physical work environment is all situations that occur related to work relationships, both relationships with superiors and relationships with colleagues, or with subordinates.

Another factor that needs to be considered in improving organizational performance is organizational culture. Organizational culture is the principal of solving external and internal problems that are carried out consistently by a group which then bequeaths to new members as the right way to understand, think about, and feel about related problems).

Meanwhile, Wibowo (2016; 15) states organizational culture as what workers perceive and how these perceptions create patterns, beliefs, values, and expectations. Furthermore, Mangkunegara (2005; 133) organizational culture is a set or assumption or belief system, values, and norms developed within the organization which serves as guidelines for behavior for its members to overcome problems of external adaptation and internal integration. Furthermore, Robbins (2013) argues that organizational culture as the dominant values disseminated in the organization is used as an employee work philosophy that guides organizational policies in managing employees and consumers. According to Robbins (2013), a strong organizational culture is a culture where the core values of the organization are held intensively and widely shared by members of the organization.

Motivation also has an impact on organizational performance. Motivation is an impulse that causes a person to do an action to achieve a certain goal. Motivation comes from the word motive which means "impulse" or stimulation or "driving force" that is in a person. According to Elliot et al. (2000), motivation is defined as an internal condition that arouses us to act, encourages us to achieve certain goals, and keeps us interested in certain activities.

According to Uno (2009), motivation can be interpreted as internal and external encouragement within a person as indicated by their existence; passions and interests; urges and needs; hopes and ideals; appreciation

and respect. Motivation becomes a force, energy or power, or a complex situation and readiness in the individual to move towards a certain goal, whether consciously or unconsciously (Makmun, 2003).

II. Literature Review

1. Work Environment

According to Nitisemito (2000: 159), the work environment is an internal and external condition that can affect morale so that work can be expected to be completed faster and better. According to Sedarmayanti (2010: 12), the conditions of the work environment are said to be good or appropriate if humans can carry out activities in an optimal, healthy, safe, and comfortable manner. The consequence of the suitability of the work environment can be seen in the long term. Furthermore, unfavorable work environments can demand more labor and time and do not support the obtaining of an efficient work system design. The type of work environment is divided into two, namely: (a) the physical work environment is a physical condition around the workplace which can affect the person directly or indirectly (b) the non-physical work environment is all situations that occur related to work relationships, both relationships with superiors and relationships with colleagues, or with subordinates. The work environment is influenced by several factors that can influence the formation of the work environment according to Sedarmayanti (2010: 46) which are as follows:

a. **Illumination / Light**

Light or lighting is very beneficial for personal to get the safety and smooth work. The light is less clear, so the work will be slow, experience many errors, and ultimately cause less efficiency in carrying out work.

b. **Air temperature**

The surrounding air is said to be dirty when the oxygen level in the air has decreased and has been mixed with gases or odors that are harmful to health, feeling cool and fresh at work will help speed up the recovery of the body due to fatigue after work.

c. **Noise**

One of the populations that are quite busy for experts to deal with is noise, which is the noise that the ear does not want. Given that work requires concentration, noise should be avoided so that work can be carried out efficiently so that work productivity increases.

d. **Job Security**

One of the efforts to maintain security in the workplace can take advantage of the Security Officer.

e. **Personal relationship**

A pleasant work environment for the person by tying a harmonious relationship with superiors, colleagues, and subordinates and supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure in the workplace will have a positive impact on the person so that personal performance can increase.

2. Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is the principal of solving external and internal problems that are carried out consistently by a group which then bequeaths to new members as the right way to understand, think about, and feel about related problems).

Wibowo (2016; 15) states organizational culture as what workers perceive and how these perceptions create patterns, beliefs, values, and expectations ". Furthermore, Mangkunegara (2011; 133) organizational culture is a set or assumption or belief system, values , and norms developed within the organization which serves as guidelines for behavior for its members to overcome problems of external adaptation and internal integration. Furthermore, Robbins (2013) argues that organizational culture as the dominant values disseminated in the organization is used as an employee work philosophy that guides organizational policies in managing employees and consumers.

There are seven classifications or dimensions of organizational culture according to Greenberg and Baron (1997) and Robbins (2013: 721). Based on the seven dimensions of organizational culture, as a whole it captures the essence of organizational culture, namely;

- a. Innovation and risk-taking, namely the degree to which organizational members are encouraged to innovate and dare to take risks.
- b. Attention to detail, namely the degree to which members of the organization show careful analysis and attention to detail.
- c. Person/individual orientation, namely the degree to which decisions are made taking into account their impact on results on people within the organization.
- d. Result orientation, namely the degree to which management focuses on the results rather than the techniques and processes used to achieve those results
- e. Cooperation orientation, namely the degree to which work activities are organized based on a team, rather than based on individual organizations.
- f. Stability is the degree to which organizational activities emphasize maintaining the status quo rather than organizational growth.
- g. Aggressiveness is the degree to which members of the organization can be aggressive, competitive, and not relaxed.

3. Motivation

Motivation is an impulse that causes a person to do an action to achieve a certain goal. Motivation comes from the word motive which means "impulse" or stimulation or "driving force" that is in a person. According to Elliot et al. (2000), motivation is defined as an internal condition that arouses us to act, encourages us to achieve certain goals, and keeps us interested in certain activities.

According to Uno (2009), motivation can be interpreted as internal and external encouragement within a person as indicated by their existence; passions and interests; urges and needs; hopes and ideals; appreciation, and respect. Motivation becomes a force, energy or power, or a complex situation and readiness in the individual to move towards a certain goal, whether consciously or unconsciously (Makmun, 2003). A person's motivation can be generated and grow through himself-intrinsically and from the extrinsic environment (Elliot et al., 2000). Intrinsic motivation means the desire of oneself to act without external stimulation (Elliott et al, 2000). Intrinsic motivation will be more profitable and provide consistency in learning. Extrinsic motivation is defined as motivation that comes from outside the individual and cannot be controlled by the individual (Howard, 1999). Maslow's theory in Handoko (2008), divides human needs as follows:

- a. **Physiological Needs**
Physiological needs are the most basic hierarchy of human needs which are the need to be able to live such as eating, drinking, housing, oxygen, sleep and so on.
- b. **Security Needs**
When the relative physiological needs are satisfied, then a second need arises, namely the need for security. The need for a sense of security includes security for protection from the dangers of work accidents, guarantees for the continuity of their work and guarantees of old age when they are no longer working.
- c. **Social Needs**
If the physiological needs and security are minimally satisfied, then there will be social needs, namely the need for friendship, affiliation and closer interaction with others. In the organization, it will be related to the need for a compact working group, good supervision, collective recreation and so on.
- d. **Needs Appreciation**
These needs include the need for the desire to be respected, valued for one's achievements, recognition of one's abilities and expertise and the effectiveness of one's work.
- e. **Self-actualization needs**
Self-actualization is Maslow's highest hierarchy of needs. Self-actualization is related to the process of developing one's true potential. The need to demonstrate one's abilities, skills and potential. The need for self-actualization tends to increase its potential because people actualize their behavior. A person who is dominated by the need for self-actualization likes tasks that challenge his abilities and expertise.

4. Organizational Performance

The definition of organizational performance refers to the ability of employees to carry out all the tasks that are their responsibility. These tasks are usually based on indicators of success that have been implemented. As a result, it will be known that an employee enters a certain level of work. The level can be various terms. Performance can be categorized as over target, on target or under target. Departing from the things referred to as a whole for the work of an employee. The definition of organizational performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an activity program or policy in realizing the goals, objectives, vision and mission of the organization as outlined in the strategic planning of an organization (Moeheriono, 2010: 60).

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In some areas of organizational performance can also be measured from other things such as strategic planning, operations, financial, legal and organizational development. Developing an institution or organization is a must to survive in the competitive climate of the world.

According to Dwiyanto (2008: 50), there are several indicators used to measure the performance of the public bureaucracy, namely as follows:

a. Productivity

The concept of productivity not only measures the level of efficiency but also effectiveness. Productivity is generally understood as the ratio between input and output. The concept of productivity was deemed too narrow and then the General Accounting Office (GAO) tried to develop a broader measure of productivity by including how much public services had expected results as an important performance indicator.

b. Quality of service.

The main data source on service quality is obtained from service users or the public in assessing service quality. Issues regarding service quality are likely to become increasingly important in explaining the performance of public service organizations. Many negative views that are formed regarding public organizations arise because of public dissatisfaction with the quality of services received from public organizations.

c. Responsiveness

Responsiveness is the organization's ability to recognize community needs to set service priorities, as well as develop public service programs according to community needs and aspirations. Responsiveness is included as one of the performance indicators because responsiveness directly describes the ability of public organizations to carry out their mission and objectives, especially to meet the needs of society. Low responsiveness is indicated by a mismatch between services and community needs. This clearly shows the failure of organizations in realizing the mission and goals of public organizations.

d. Responsibility

Responsibility describes whether the implementation of the activities of a public organization is carried out following correct administrative principles or following organizational policies. This can be assessed from

the analysis of documents and reports on organizational activities by matching the implementation of organizational activities and programs with organizational procedures and requirements in the organization.

e. Accountability

Public accountability refers to the extent to which the policies and activities of public organizations are subject to public officials elected by the people. The assumption is that these political officials are elected because they are elected by the people, by itself will always represent the interests of the people. In this context, the basic concept of public accountability can be used to see how much the policies and activities of public organizations are consistent with the will of the public at large. The performance of public organizations can not only be seen from the internal measures developed by public organizations or governments, such as the achievement of targets. Performance should be assessed from external measures, such as values and norms that apply in society.

III. Research Methods

Time and Location of Research

The research will be conducted in October-December 2019 by taking the location at PT. Semen Baturaja (Persero).

Research Design

This study uses an explanatory analysis approach. This means that every variable presented in the hypothesis will be observed through testing the causal relationship of the independent variable to the dependent variable. The relationship between variables can be described in the form of a path analysis diagram as follows: The research conceptual framework can be explained as follows:

Figure 1. Overall Path Analysis

Population and sample

The population in this research are employees who work at the PT. Semen Baturaja (Persero). While the sample used includes 114 employees who work in company offices. This sampling uses the saturated sample method because it uses all employees at the company office.

The research instrument uses a questionnaire which will be arranged based on predetermined dimensions.

Data Source

To obtain concrete and objective data, research must be conducted on the problem under study, while the steps that the researcher takes in data collection are:

a. Primary data

Primary data is data obtained directly from the object of research. In this case, primary data is obtained from field research, namely the data collection method which is carried out by direct research on the object of research in question.

b. Secondary data

Secondary data is data obtained indirectly from the object of research. In this case, secondary data is obtained from the research library, namely the method of collecting data by studying and understanding literary books created by authors who can be justified in their theoretical basis.

Data Analysis Technique

The stages of data processing in this study are the classic assumption test with regression such as linearity test, heteroscedasticity test, normality test, multicollinearity and autocorrelation test as well as search for descriptive statistics, namely the average value, median mode, standard deviation and range.

Data Quality Test

The questionnaire that will be used in the research, to produce a valid and reliable instrument, is first tested with the validity and reliability of the instrument. According to Sugiyono (2007: 219) "Validity is a condition that describes the level of the instrument concerned can measure what should be measured". Meanwhile, reliability is a value that shows the consistency of a measuring device in measuring the same symptoms (Riduwan, 2011: 86). By using valid and reliable instruments, it is expected that the research results will be valid and reliable.

Research Results and Discussion

1. Influence of Work Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance Partially

Based on the analysis, it is known that the coefficient of organizational culture is 0.654. The t value is 9,143. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the work organizational culture variable affects organizational performance partially. The magnitude of the influence of work organizational culture on organizational performance can be obtained by the value of r squared of 0.427. This means that the influence of work organizational culture variables on organizational performance is 42.7% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

2. Influence of Motivation on Organizational Performance

The results of the analysis of the effect of motivation on performance partially show that the motivation coefficient is 0.861. The t value is 17.904. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the motivation variable partially affects organizational performance. The magnitude of the influence of motivation on organizational performance is known to be the value of r squared of 0.741. This means that the influence of the motivation variable on organizational performance is 74.1% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

3. Influence of the work environment on motivation

The results of the analysis of the influence of the work environment on motivation partially show that the coefficient of the work environment is 0.669. The t value is 9,520. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that work environment variables partially influence motivation. The magnitude of the influence of the work environment on motivation, it is known that the value of r squared is 0.447. This means that the influence of the motivation variable on organizational performance is 44.7% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

4. Influence of Organizational Culture on Motivation

The results of the analysis of the influence of organizational culture on motivation partially show that the coefficient of organizational culture is 0.780. The t value is 13,205. The significant value is 0.00. This significant value is smaller than 0.05. This means that the variable organizational culture partially affects

motivation. The magnitude of the influence of organizational culture on motivation is known to be the value of r squared of 0.609. This means that the influence of organizational culture on motivation is 60.9% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

5. Influence of Work Environment on Organizational Performance through Motivation Variables

Based on the path analysis, it is known that the influence of the work environment on organizational performance is 0.532. The influence of the work environment on performance through motivation is $0.669 \times 0.861 = 0.576$. In this case the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect, so it can be said that the work motivation variable is intervening.

6. Influence of Work Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance through Motivation Variables

Based on the path analysis, it is known that the direct influence of work organizational culture on organizational performance is 0.654. While the influence of work organizational culture on organizational performance through motivation is $0.780 \times 0.861 = 0.672$. In this case, the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect, so it can be said that the work motivation variable is intervening.

Figure 2. Path Analysis Results

IV. Conclusions and Suggestion

Conclusion

Work environment variables partially influence organizational performance. The value of r squared is 0.273. This means that the influence of work environment variables on performance is 27.3% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

Work organizational culture variables partially influence organizational performance. The value of r squared is 0.427. This means that the influence of work organizational culture variables on organizational performance is 42.7% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

Motivation variables partially influence organizational performance. The value of r squared is 0.741. This means that the influence of the motivation variable on organizational performance is 74.1% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

Work environment variables partially influence motivation. The value of r squared is 0.447. This means that the influence of the motivation variable on organizational performance is 44.7% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

Organizational culture variables affect motivation partially. The value of r squared is 0.609. This means that the influence of organizational culture on motivation is 60.9% and the rest is influenced by other variables that are not included in the equation model.

The influence of the work environment on organizational performance is 0.532. The influence of the work environment on performance through motivation is $0.669 \times 0.861 = 0.576$. In this case the indirect effect is greater than the direct effect, so it can be said that the work motivation variable is intervening.

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Suggestion

In increasing organizational performance, it is necessary to develop the environment, organizational culture and motivation of employees at work. The environment must be improved by maintaining cleanliness, improving facilities and infrastructure at work and improving relations with employees.

The organizational culture is improved through the mental coaching of employees through meetings, joint events and strict implementation of policies. This needs to be done to shape employee habits so that they are in line with the company culture.

Motivation also needs to be improved by paying attention to employee income, non-financial employee needs and improving employee relations with superiors and employees with other employees.

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